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The Innovation Input Sub-Index on a Global Scale

Between 2013 and 2022 it decreased by an average of 5.76% for the countries analysed

The Innovation Input Sub-Index is a fundamental part of the Global Innovation Index (GII), measuring a country's capacity to generate innovation. This sub-index focuses on inputs, which are the resources and conditions necessary to foster innovation. It takes into account five main aspects. First, it evaluates institutions, including the quality of political, regulatory, and commercial institutions, which are essential for creating an environment conducive to innovation. These include factors such as political stability, government effectiveness, and the regulatory framework. Second, it analyzes human capital and research, measuring investment in education, the quality of the educational system, and the availability of advanced research. This aspect includes indicators such as enrollment rates, public expenditure on education, and the number of active researchers. Another fundamental aspect is infrastructure, which assesses the quality of both physical and digital infrastructure, indispensable for innovation. Factors such as access to information and communication technologies (ICT), environmental sustainability, and the quality of transportation and logistics infrastructure are considered. Market sophistication is another key element, measuring the maturity of the financial market, the availability of credit and venture capital, and the ease of doing business. This aspect examines how simple it is for companies to access the financing needed for innovation. Finally, business sophistication is assessed to understand the level of sophistication of companies, including their ability to absorb knowledge, innovate internally, and collaborate with other companies. This also includes the ability to attract talent and leverage technology. The Innovation Input Sub-Index is crucial because it provides a comprehensive view of the structural conditions that support innovation. A high score in this sub-index indicates that a country is well-prepared to sustain innovative processes, although this does not necessarily guarantee a high level of innovative output. However, it is an essential component for understanding how predisposed a country is to developing and implementing new ideas and technologies.

The Innovation Input Sub-Index in 2022. At the top of the ranking is Singapore, with a score of 70.6, followed by the United States with 69 and Switzerland with 67.5. These countries are recognized for their strong institutions, advanced infrastructure, market and business sophistication, as well as strong human capital and research. Their success in the Innovation Input Sub-Index is not surprising, given the high quality of their political and regulatory institutions, consistent investment in education and research, and highly developed economies. The United States, in second place, demonstrates excellence in business support and the availability of resources for research and development. This reflects the crucial role of highly qualified human capital and advanced technological infrastructure in maintaining a fertile environment for innovation. Switzerland, with a score of 67.5, is often seen as a model of institutional efficiency and quality, with a strong tradition of research and a private sector that invests heavily in innovation. Following are countries like Sweden (66.3), Hong Kong (65.3), and Finland (64.5), which are known for their excellent educational structures, research support policies, and economic systems that facilitate innovation. Sweden, in particular, stands out for its ability to combine a high standard of living with a highly innovative environment, thanks to policies that promote creativity and entrepreneurship. Hong Kong, due to its position as a financial and commercial hub, benefits from a sophisticated market that attracts global capital and talent, while

Finland stands out for its continued investment in education and research. The United Kingdom (63.6) and Denmark (62.8) are two more examples of countries that, despite their relatively small size, excel in the Innovation Input Sub-Index. The United Kingdom, with its world-class universities and an economic environment favorable to innovation, continues to be a global leader in this field. Denmark, with its strong welfare state and policies that promote a balance between work and personal life, creates an environment where innovation can thrive, supported by a high level of trust in institutions. Canada (62.5) and the Netherlands (62.4) follow closely, with highly developed economies that offer a stable and favorable environment for innovation. Both countries boast a strong educational system, a high degree of market sophistication, and solid business support, elements reflected in their high scores in the Innovation Input Sub-Index. Among Asian countries, besides Singapore and Hong Kong, Japan (61.4) and South Korea (60.6) also stand out for their performances. Japan, known for its technological innovations and advanced industry, continues to be a global leader, although its score suggests there may be room for improvement in some areas. South Korea, which has made enormous progress in innovation in recent decades, reflects a consistent commitment to improving its infrastructure and human capital. Among European countries, Germany (60.9) and France (60.9) maintain strong positions, thanks to diversified economies and policies that support research and development. Germany, with its robust manufacturing sector and highly advanced vocational training system, continues to be an innovation powerhouse in Europe. France, with its high-quality education system and extensive network of research institutes, confirms itself as one of the main players in global innovation. Estonia (60.7), a relatively small but highly digitalized country, demonstrates that even smaller nations can excel in innovation if supported by smart policies and a strong commitment to digitalization and education. This positioning is particularly noteworthy considering the country's limited size and resources. The analysis of countries with lower scores highlights the significant challenges they face. Countries like Nigeria (25.3), Burkina Faso (25.2), and Yemen (19.2) are at the bottom of the ranking, reflecting a lack of infrastructure, a low level of qualified human capital, and often unstable or ineffective institutions. These factors make it difficult for these countries to create an environment conducive to innovation. The low availability of resources for education and research, combined with underdeveloped markets, contributes to limiting these countries' ability to attract the investments and talent needed for innovative development. Italy, with a score of 48.9, is positioned in an intermediate position, suggesting that despite a diversified economy and a good level of human capital, the country could benefit from further structural reforms to improve its innovative environment. Italy's low position can be attributed to a combination of factors, including bureaucracy, a certain rigidity in the labor market, and an educational system that may require more investment, especially in terms of research and development.

The Innovation Input Sub-Index Between 2013 and 2022. At the top of the list of improvements are countries like China, India, Uzbekistan, and Indonesia, which have recorded significant increases in their Innovation Input Sub-Index scores. China, in particular, has shown an absolute increase of 12.3 points, equivalent to a 27.21% increase. This improvement can be attributed to several factors, including massive investment in research and development, government policies favorable to innovation, and growing attention to higher education and vocational training. India, with a 23.18% increase, reflects a similar trend, albeit on a slightly smaller scale. This progress can be seen as a result of economic reforms, opening up to the global market, and investments in digital technologies. Countries like Uzbekistan and Indonesia have also shown significant improvements, with increases of 20% and 17.89%, respectively. These increases can be associated with domestic policies aimed at improving access to education, enhancing infrastructure, and creating a more competitive economic environment. However, it is important to note that despite these advances, the absolute scores of these countries remain relatively low compared to more developed nations, indicating that while progress

has been made, much remains to be done to reach the global leaders in innovation. Another group of countries, including Vietnam, Pakistan, and the Philippines, has recorded moderate increases in the index, with percentage increases ranging from 10% to 13%. These improvements suggest steady and consistent progress, although not revolutionary, reflecting likely gradual improvements in the economic environment and government policies oriented towards innovation. An interesting case is represented by the United Arab Emirates, Estonia, and Malta, countries that already have a relatively high score and continue to improve, albeit with more modest percentage increases. The United Arab Emirates, for example, recorded a 10% increase, reflecting the country's continued commitment to diversifying its economy and investing in high-tech sectors. Estonia, with an 8.98% increase, continues to strengthen its reputation as a leader in digital innovation and information technologies. On the other hand, some of the more developed countries, such as France, Germany, and Switzerland, have shown only slight improvements, with percentage increases below 5%. This may suggest that these countries, already leaders in innovation, are reaching a plateau, where further improvements become more difficult to achieve. However, their relatively high position in the index demonstrates that they continue to maintain a strongly favorable environment for innovation. In contrast, numerous countries have recorded a decline in their scores, indicating difficulties in maintaining or improving their innovation-friendly environment. Among these countries, the United States has seen a slight decrease in its score, with a 0.29% drop. This marginal decline may reflect the growing challenges the country faces in maintaining its position as a global leader in innovation, despite continued investments in technology and research. Japan, Singapore, and South Korea, known for being technological powerhouses, have all recorded decreases in their scores, with drops of 2.23%, 2.35%, and 2.42%, respectively. These declines, though not dramatic, could indicate structural challenges or saturation in their respective innovation environments. For example, Japan may face difficulties due to an aging population and a rigid economic structure that makes it difficult to adopt new ideas. Singapore, on the other hand, may face limitations related to its geographic size and dependence on highly qualified human resources, while South Korea may be influenced by increasingly fierce global competition. Another significant group of countries that have experienced decreases includes European nations such as the Netherlands, Finland, Norway, and Denmark. The declines recorded by these countries, ranging from 2.8% to 5.28%, may suggest a reduction in the capacity to maintain the pace of innovation in the face of increasing global economic pressures and internal demographic changes. For example, Finland, which saw a 3.3% drop, may be facing challenges related to an evolving labor market and the need to renew its economic model. Countries like Greece, Slovenia, and Slovakia have recorded more significant declines, with decreases ranging from 5% to 9%. These declines can be attributed to economic crises, political instability, or insufficient investments in innovative infrastructure. For example, Greece has suffered for years due to the sovereign debt crisis, which has limited the country's ability to invest in crucial sectors for innovation. One of the most concerning aspects involves countries that have recorded the most significant declines, many of which are located in developing regions or are characterized by political and economic instability. Among these, Ireland saw an 8.3% decrease in its score, a surprising figure for a country often considered a hub for global tech companies. This decline could reflect internal challenges such as rising living costs and difficulties in attracting international talent, which could dampen the country's attractiveness as an innovation center. Another group of countries that has seen alarming declines includes African nations like Uganda, Mozambique, and Guinea, which have experienced decreases of over 20%. These results indicate severe structural difficulties that prevent these countries from developing an innovation-friendly environment. Lack of infrastructure, political instability, and widespread poverty are factors likely contributing to these declines. The most significant decline was recorded by Guatemala, with a 30.4% decrease, suggesting that the country is facing deep challenges that hinder any progress in innovation.

Economic Policies for the Innovation Input Sub-Index. Economic policies aimed at increasing the value of the Innovation Input Sub-Index should focus on a series of strategic interventions that improve the structural, institutional, and financial conditions of a country, thereby creating a more favorable environment for innovation. First and foremost, it is essential to invest heavily in human capital. This means strengthening the education system at all levels, from primary education to university, with a particular emphasis on STEM disciplines (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics). However, it is not enough to simply increase the number of graduates; it is necessary to ensure that education is of high quality, accessible, and closely aligned with the needs of the labor market. This requires a continuous reform of curricula to align students' skills with the current and future challenges of the workforce, while also promoting lifelong learning. In parallel, it is crucial to support scientific research and innovation through increased public and private investment in research and development (R&D). Governments can incentivize such investments through tax benefits, direct grants, and support policies for the creation of public-private partnerships, fostering collaboration between universities, research centers, and businesses. In this context, it is also essential to promote a culture of innovation within companies by supporting the initiative and creativity of workers and facilitating access to cutting-edge technologies and innovative production processes. In addition to investing in human capital and R&D, another crucial element for improving the Innovation Input Sub-Index is the quality of infrastructure, both physical and digital. Efficient transport infrastructure, sustainable energy systems, and an advanced telecommunications network are all essential components for creating an environment that fosters innovation. In particular, digital infrastructure plays an increasingly important role. Expanding access to high-speed Internet and ensuring the widespread adoption of digital technologies, such as 5G networks and artificial intelligence platforms, can significantly enhance a country's ability to attract investments and talent, fostering the growth of startups and innovative businesses. Therefore, economic policies should include strategic plans for the expansion and improvement of digital infrastructure, including digital literacy programs to ensure that the population and businesses can fully exploit new technologies. Institutions, another pillar of the Innovation Input Sub-Index, must be efficient, transparent, and stable to create an environment that fosters innovation. Effective governance, respect for the rule of law, and a business-friendly regulatory system are elements that can incentivize investments and entrepreneurial creativity. Institutional reforms should aim to reduce bureaucracy, simplify procedures for starting a business, and improve the transparency and accountability of public institutions. Additionally, it is fundamental to ensure an effective and impartial judicial system capable of protecting intellectual property rights and enforcing contracts, as these are critical aspects for attracting investors and incentivizing innovation. Another key factor is market sophistication, which relates to the financial system's ability to support innovation through the provision of credit, venture capital, and other financial instruments. To improve this aspect, economic policies should promote a dynamic financial environment where banks and investors are willing to finance innovative, albeit risky, projects. Governments can facilitate this process through the creation of public venture capital funds, support for crowdfunding platforms, and the provision of loan guarantees for startups. Furthermore, financial regulation should be calibrated to balance the stability of the system with the need to support innovation. For example, more flexible regulations for new enterprises, such as those in the fintech sector, can stimulate competition and innovation within the financial industry. Another critical area is business sophistication, which concerns companies' ability to adopt and develop new technologies, as well as collaborate with other businesses and institutions to innovate. Economic policies should therefore incentivize the adoption of advanced technologies and promote the creation of collaboration networks between companies, universities, and research centers. This can be achieved through the creation of industrial clusters, technology parks, and startup incubators, which facilitate the meeting between innovators and investors, as well as the sharing of knowledge and resources. Policies should also

encourage the internationalization of businesses, facilitating access to global markets and promoting participation in international innovation networks. Finally, a often overlooked but crucial aspect for improving the Innovation Input Sub-Index is the promotion of environmental sustainability as a driver of innovation. Economic policies should incentivize the adoption of sustainable practices, both in businesses and at the level of national infrastructure. This can include tax incentives for companies investing in clean technologies, the promotion of renewable energy, and the development of smart and sustainable cities. The transition to a low-carbon economy not only helps mitigate climate change but also offers significant opportunities for innovation in sectors such as energy, transportation, and construction. Moreover, the link between sustainability and innovation is increasingly recognized at the international level, and countries that adopt innovative policies in this area can not only improve their Innovation Input Sub-Index but also position themselves as global leaders in the ecological transition.

Conclusions. The value of the Innovation Input Sub-Index decreased by an average of 5.76% for the countries analyzed between 2013 and 2022, dropping from 43.11 units to 40.63 units. However, there are countries that have recorded a much higher value of the Innovation Input Sub-Index compared to the period average, such as China with +27.21%, India with +23.18%, Uzbekistan with +20.00%, Indonesia with +17.89%, and Iran Islamic Republic with +12.65%. There are also countries where the value of the Innovation Input Sub-Index has decreased significantly, such as Trinidad and Tobago with -20.79%, Tobago with -21.14%, Uganda with -22.81%, Mozambique with -26.18%, and Guatemala with -30.40%.

Country	2022	Country	2022	Country	2022
Singapore	70,6	Greece	43	Morocco	33,2
United States	69	Croatia	42,7	Jamaica	33
Switzerland	67,5	Russian Federation	42,6	Tunisia	33
Sweden	66,3	Bulgaria	42,2	Dominican Republic	32,7
Hong Kong SAR, China	65,3	Thailand	42,2	Rwanda	31,6
Finland	64,5	Turkiye	41,8	Cambodia	31,4
United Kingdom	63,6	Bahrain	41,6	Senegal	30,9
Denmark	62,8	Montenegro	41,6	Paraguay	30,8
Canada	62,5	Peru	41,5	Trinidad and Tobago	30,1
Netherlands	62,4	Brunei Darussalam	41,2	Ecuador	29,7
Japan	61,4	Slovak Republic	41,1	Egypt, Arab Rep.	29,2
Germany	60,9	Serbia	40,9	Lao PDR	28,8
France	60,9	Romania	40,5	Nicaragua	28,8
Norway	60,8	Uruguay	40,5	Tanzania	28,7
Estonia	60,7	Brazil	40,4	Sri Lanka	28,6
Korea, Rep.	60,6	Vietnam	40,1	El Salvador	28,6
Austria	59,6	North Macedonia	39,9	Kenya	28,1
United Arab Emirates	59,4	Georgia	39,6	Ghana	27,8
Australia	59,3	Oman	39,5	Tajikistan	27,8
China	57,5	Colombia	39,2	Benin	27,6
Luxembourg	57,5	Bosnia and Herzegovina	38,7	Nepal	27,6
Israel	57,3	Kazakhstan	38,4	Honduras	27,5
New Zealand	57,1	Costa Rica	38,2	Cote d'Ivoire	27,1
Iceland	55,9	Kuwait	38,2	Algeria	26,7
Ireland	55,8	Uzbekistan	37,8	Bangladesh	26,5
Belgium	55,3	Mexico	37,5	Pakistan	26,5
Malta	52,9	South Africa	37,5	Nigeria	25,3
Spain	51,8	Jordan	37,2	Burkina Faso	25,2
Cyprus	51,3	Indonesia	36,9	Togo	24,7
Slovenia	50,2	Botswana	36,5	Uganda	24,7
Italy	48,9	Iran, Islamic Rep.	36,5	Guatemala	24,5
Portugal	48,5	Philippines	35,7	Zambia	24,5
Czechia	48,4	Ukraine	35,7	Niger	24
Lithuania	48,1	Argentina	35,6	Zimbabwe	23,9
Malaysia	48	Albania	35,3	Mauritania	23,7
Hungary	46,9	Azerbaijan	35,3	Myanmar	23,4
Saudi Arabia	46,5	Moldova	35,3	Mozambique	23,4
Qatar	45,8	Mongolia	34,7	Cameroon	23
Latvia	44,8	Armenia	34,3	Madagascar	22,9
Mauritius	44,4	Panama	34,1	Ethiopia	22,6
Poland	44,3	Namibia	33,8	Burundi	22,2
India	44,1	Belarus	33,7	Mali	21,9
Chile	43,7	Kyrgyz Republic	33,7	Angola	21,1

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